

Community Mapping and Participation Processes in Aotearoa New Zealand

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1. Introduction

In the island nation of Aotearoa New Zealand, there have been several waves of migration, beginning with Māori, who arrived from the Polynesian islands 1000 years ago. The next stage of migration started in the 1840s, following the signing of the Treaty of Waitangi between Māori and the British Crown. These migrants, whom the Māori referred to as Pākehā, were mainly from the British Isles. In the 1860s, discoveries in the Otago goldfields attracted Chinese immigrants who established themselves as gold miners and traders. From 1910 onward, people from the Pacific Islands began to migrate to New Zealand (Thompson, 2000).

In the 21st century, we are facing new threats to public open space - not of disuse, but of patterns of design and management that exclude some people and serve to reduce cultural diversity.

Figure 1. Gap and opportunity

In the above situations, exploring how people from different ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand can be fully integrated into the public open space is critical (Figure 1).

2. Literature

From a sociological viewpoint, place is a unique spot in the universe; its physicality with people and investment of meaning and value makes a place meaningful (Gieryn, 2000). Then, a good relationship is created and developed through long-time connections between a person and place in a particular locality, which is described as sense of place (Lynch, 1990).

Why search for the community? Firstly, community is always treated as a synonym for place and an essential aspect of the sense of place (National Academy of Sciences, 2002). Moreover, *“people spend most of their time and meet most of their needs within local ecologies, and the community is the smallest form of society and the most comprehensive social unit one can experience first-hand”* (Wilkinson, 1986, p. 3).

Community participation in planning is centred on the principle that the community improves when its members are actively involved into the participation process of planning, rather than just being treated as the unrelated inhabitants living there (Sanoff, 2006).

The four major ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand are considered in this research (Figure 2), including New Zealand European, Māori, Chinese and Pasifika (Statistics New Zealand, 2019). Each of them has a specific background and perspective.

Figure 2. Major ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand

In summary, community participation for public open space planning can provide opportunities for potential interactions in decision making process so as to help stimulate sense of community. More importantly, these four New Zealand ethnic groups represent a diversity of community interests and needs, which participatory processes can respond to and draw out for representation in public space planning and design. This research grapples with the issue of how this can best be achieved in the context of this diverse cultural makeup in Aotearoa New Zealand.

3. Method

First, the online survey, written to incorporate the Sense of Community Index-2, was conducted through the Qualtrics online platform and distributed intermittently in New Zealand via web-based channels during a nine-month period in 2020-21. A snowball sampling method was utilised, leading to 172 responses. When removing incomplete and invalid responses, we were left with 145 eligible responses to analyse.

Table 1. Measurements and analysis methods for survey

Measurements		Data Analysis Methods
<i>Sense of Community Index</i>	<i>Reliability Analysis</i>	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Sample Description (Age, Gender, Educational Background, Ethnicity)</i>		Descriptive Analysis
<i>Sense of Community Index</i>	1) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Multifactor ANOVA
	2) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Descriptive Analysis
	3) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Independent Sample T-test

For this survey, the data were coded and analysed by using IBM SPSS Statistics 28 (Table 1).

Second, throughout all focus group sessions, the researcher took precautions to ensure that ethical and cultural issues were considered and protected. To build the relationship of trust and connection, the researcher was advised by several local residents' associations, community centres and city councils.

Table 2. General description of focus groups

Community	Ethnic Group	Location	Number
Newtown	New Zealand European	Newtown Community Hall	3
		Newtown Community Centre	2
	Chinese	Online	4
Porirua	New Zealand European	Online	4
	Māori	Online	3
	Chinese	Online	3
		Online	2
	Pasifika	City Hub, Porirua	2
	Online	7	

Table 2 presents the general description of all focus group sessions. Each focus group was arranged exclusively for participants from that ethnic community. Moreover, the six numbers in Table 3 represent the six participation methods concluded from the literature.

Table 3. Participation methods coding

Coding	Participation Methods
No. 1	Participatory Mapping
No. 2	Guided Tour
No. 3	Focus Group
No. 4	3D Visualisation
No. 5	Interactive Planning
No. 6	Visual Preference Survey

Numbers 1 to 3 represent the prioritisation of the effective participation methods selected by the participants during the focus groups. Participants rated the effectiveness of those methods, from No. 1 - extremely effective to No. 3 - slightly effective (Table 4).

Table 4. Scale of effectiveness

Coding	Scale
①	Extremely Effective
②	Moderately Effective
③	Slightly Effective

A total number of 30 participants were recruited for this research, including New Zealand European, Māori, Chinese and Pasifika.

4. Findings and Discussion for the First Phase of Online Survey

This first phase of study investigates the Sense of Community Index-2 scores for four New Zealand ethnic groups concerning their participation in community planning of public open spaces.

In the context of Aotearoa New Zealand, the analysis provides strong evidence that people's sense of community is significantly higher for those who participated in the participatory planning process of community public open spaces, than for those who have not participated (Figure 3). It is consistent with the literature based on other contexts that the residents of the focused communities developed with significant participatory planning have a stronger sense of community, which is attributed to the participatory planning process (Valle, 2008).

Figure 3. Between-Group comparisons of mean SCI-2 scores

This first phase of research provides the platform and opportunity for this research to be extended into a second phase, where the intention is to explore a series of community participation methods with each of the four ethnic groups, aiming to evaluate their effectiveness.

5. Findings and Discussion for the Second Phase of Focus Groups

This second phase of focus groups examined the experiences of the community member's participation process and explored the effectiveness of the participation methods in relation to their ethnicity and cultural background (Table 5).

Table 5. Different series of effective participation methods by ethnicity

Ethnic Group	No. 1	No. 2	No. 3	No. 4	No. 5	No. 6	hui	talanoa
New Zealand European		③		①		②		
Māori		①	②			③	★	
Chinese		③		②		①		
Pasifika		①		③	②			★

The cultural relationships and background for the selections are explored and discovered through the focus group data. Focus group findings indicate the importance of the cultural role in the selection of the most effective community participation methods by targeting ethnic groups: 1) for New Zealand Europeans, their selection of the highly effective participation method is a representation of their cultural viewpoint and pursuit toward new technology and innovation; 2) for Māori, their selection of the highly effective participation method is closed

related with their Indigenous history, connections to the land and the distinctive pursuit of health and wellbeing; 3) for Chinese, their selection of the most effective method and their cultural element of collectivism are inner connected; and 4) for Pasifika, their selection of the highly effective method is connected to their cultural component of interactivity.

The findings also reveal similarities and differences in the selections of all the targeting ethnic groups, including the least effective participation method and a different series of relatively effective participation methods. For the least effective participation method, findings highlight that participatory mapping is selected as the least effective community participation method for all four ethnic groups in this research. Generally speaking, this method is standard to designers but is not necessarily applicable to non-professional community members. For the series of relatively effective participation methods, it is suggested that different combinations and series of participation methods should be embraced for different ethnic groups.

Note

Responsible Author: Yiwen Cui

This paper is based on two published papers as below:

1. Cui, Y., Gjerde, M., & Marques, B. (2023). Encouraging sense of community in Aotearoa New Zealand: exploring the role of community participation in public open space planning. *Cities & Health*, 8(4), 566–575. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23748834.2023.2230619>
2. Cui, Y., Gjerde, M., & Marques, B. (2024). Mapping and Assessing Effective Participatory Planning Processes for Urban Green Spaces in Aotearoa New Zealand's Diverse Communities. *Land*, 13(9), 1412. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land13091412>

References

- Gieryn, T. F. (2000). A Space for Place in Sociology. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 26, 463–496.
- Lynch, K. (1990). *Good City Form*. The M.I.T. Press.
- National Academy of Sciences. (2002). *Community and Quality of Life: Data Needs for Informed Decision Making*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press.
- Sanoff, H. (2006). Multiple Views of Participatory Design. *Journal of the Faculty of Architecture*, 23(2), 11–21.
- Statistics New Zealand. (2019). *2018 Census population and dwelling counts*. Stats NZ.
- Thompson, K. (2000). A Sense of Place and Identity in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Textile Society of America Symposium*, 179–184.
- Valle, E. (2008). Sense of Community: A Comparative Study of Two Design Methods - New Urbanism and Participatory Design. *Focus*, 5(1), 37–40.
- Wilkinson, K. P. (1986). In search of the Community in the Changing Countryside. *Rural Sociology*, 51(1), 1–17.